

Possible futures for Urban East Africa under a changing climate

The impacts of climate change will vary across the region according to a range of local factors. Which of these impacts could be felt in your community in these three different climates?

Possible Futures

- FUTURE 1** Much wetter, large increase in heavy rainfall and hotter
- FUTURE 2** Increase in extreme rainfall and hotter
- FUTURE 3** Much hotter and drier with more erratic rainy seasons

Intensity of Impact

- Low** (1 dot)
- Medium** (2 dots)
- High** (3 dots)

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